

**ILMIY VA
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TERAPIYA**

**SCIENTIFIC >>> >>>
AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

2026, № 2 (Март-Апрель)

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**SCIENTIFIC AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

**ИЛМИЙ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН
ТЕРАПИЯ**

**НАУЧНАЯ И ИННОВАЦИОННАЯ
ТЕРАПИЯ**

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Morphological changes in the uterus under chronic carbon monoxide exposure in experimental animals

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Abstract. Carbon monoxide (CO) is one of the most common toxic gases formed during incomplete combustion and poses a serious threat to both human and animal health. The main pathogenic mechanism of carbon monoxide is associated with its high affinity to hemoglobin, leading to tissue hypoxia. Chronic hypoxia may cause structural and functional alterations in various organs and tissues. However, the effect of carbon monoxide on the female reproductive system, particularly on uterine tissues, remains insufficiently studied. The aim of this study was to investigate morphological and morphometric changes in the uterus under chronic exposure to carbon monoxide in experimental animals. The study was conducted on 40 white laboratory rats divided into control and experimental groups. Morphological alterations in uterine tissues were evaluated using histological and morphometric methods. The results demonstrated a decrease in endometrial and myometrial thickness, a reduction in the number of uterine glands, and an increase in vascular density under carbon monoxide exposure. These findings indicate that chronic exposure to carbon monoxide leads to significant structural changes in the uterus and may negatively affect reproductive function.

Keywords: carbon monoxide, uterus, morphology, hypoxia, experimental study, reproductive organ.

Морфологические изменения матки при хроническом воздействии угарного газа в эксперименте

Рузиева Гулрух Маратовна, Джумаев Каромат Шойимович

Аннотация. Угарный газ (СО) является одним из наиболее распространённых токсических газов, образующихся при неполном сгорании органических веществ, и представляет серьёзную угрозу для организма человека и животных. Основным механизмом его патогенного действия связан с высокой аффинностью к гемоглобину, что приводит к развитию тканевой гипоксии. Хроническая гипоксия может вызывать морфологические изменения в различных органах и тканях. Однако влияние угарного газа на органы женской репродуктивной системы, в частности на ткани матки, изучено недостаточно. Целью данного исследования являлось изучение морфологических и морфометрических изменений матки при хроническом воздействии угарного газа в эксперименте. Исследование проведено на 40 белых лабораторных крысах, разделённых на контрольную и экспериментальные группы. Морфологические изменения в тканях матки оценивались с использованием гистологических и морфометрических методов. Полученные результаты показали снижение толщины эндометрия и миометрия, уменьшение количества маточных желез и увеличение сосудистой плотности при воздействии угарного газа. Полученные данные свидетельствуют о том, что хроническое воздействие угарного газа вызывает значительные морфологические изменения в тканях матки и может негативно влиять на репродуктивную функцию.

Ключевые слова: угарный газ, матка, морфология, гипоксия, экспериментальное исследование, репродуктивные органы.

**Экспериментал ҳайвонларда сурункали ис гази таъсирида бачадонда юз
берадиган морфологик ўзгаришлар**

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Аннотация. Ис гази (СО) ноқис ёнув жараёнида ҳосил бўладиган энг кенг тарқалган токсик газлардан бири бўлиб, инсон ва ҳайвонлар организми учун жиддий хавф туғдиради. Унинг асосий патогенетик таъсири гемоглобин билан юқори аффинитетга эга бўлиб, тўқималарда гипоксия ҳолатини келтириб чиқариши билан боғлиқ. Суранкали гипоксия турли орган ва тўқималарда морфологик ўзгаришларга сабаб бўлади. Бироқ ис газининг аёллар репродуктив тизимига, хусусан бачадон тўқималарига таъсири етарлича ўрганилмаган. Ушбу тадқиқотнинг мақсади экспериментал ҳайвонларда сурункали ис гази таъсири натижасида бачадонда юз берадиган морфологик ва морфометрик ўзгаришларни ўрганишдан иборат. Тадқиқот 40 та оқ лаборатория каламушларида ўтказилди. Ҳайвонлар назорат ва тажриба гуруҳларига бўлинди. Бачадон тўқималаридаги морфологик ўзгаришлар гистологик ва морфометрик усуллар ёрдамида баҳоланди. Натижалар ис гази таъсирида эндометрий ва миометрий қалинлигининг камайиши, безлар сонининг пасайиши ҳамда қон томирлар зичлигининг ошиши кузатилишини кўрсатди. Олинган маълумотлар ис гази таъсири бачадон тўқималарида сезиларли морфологик ўзгаришларни келтириб чиқариши ва репродуктив функцияга салбий таъсир кўрсатиши мумкинлигини кўрсатади..

Калим сўзлар: *ис гази, бачадон, морфология, гипоксия, экспериментал тадқиқот, репродуктив органлар*

Introduction. Environmental pollution remains a major global health problem. Among toxic gases, carbon monoxide occupies a special place due to its high affinity for hemoglobin and its ability to induce tissue hypoxia[2,3].

Carbon monoxide is produced during incomplete combustion of organic materials such as coal, gasoline, wood, and natural gas. Chronic exposure to CO can cause pathological changes in many organs, including the brain, heart, liver, and kidneys. However, its effect on reproductive organs has not been fully investigated[5,6].

The uterus is a highly vascularized organ that plays a key role in reproduction. Any structural alteration in uterine tissues may lead to impaired reproductive function. Hypoxia caused by carbon monoxide may significantly affect the histological structure of the uterus[1,4].

Therefore, studying morphological changes in the uterus under CO exposure is important for understanding its impact on female reproductive health.

The aim of this study was to investigate morphometric and histological changes in the uterus under chronic carbon monoxide exposure.

Materials and Methods. The present experimental study was carried out on 40 female white laboratory rats weighing 180–220 g and aged 8–10 weeks. All animals were kept under standard laboratory conditions with a temperature of 22–24°C, relative humidity of 50–60%, and a 12-hour light/dark cycle. The animals had free access to standard laboratory food and drinking water throughout the experiment.

The experimental procedures were conducted in accordance with international ethical guidelines for the use of laboratory animals.

The animals were randomly divided into four groups (n = 10 each): one control group and three experimental groups exposed to different concentrations of carbon monoxide.

Table 1

Experimental groups and exposure conditions

Procedure	Reagent	Duration
Fixation	10% formalin	24 h
Dehydration	Ethanol (70–100%)	12 h

Clearing	Xylene	2 h
Embedding	Paraffin	3 h
Section thickness	Microtome	5 μ m
Staining	Hematoxylin–Eosin	standard protocol

Carbon monoxide exposure was performed in a specially designed chamber where the gas concentration was continuously monitored.

Tissue sampling. The end of the experimental period, the animals were anesthetized and euthanized according to ethical standards. The uterine tissues were carefully removed and washed with physiological saline.

The samples were fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin for 24 hours.

Histological examination

After fixation, the tissues were processed using standard histological techniques. The samples were dehydrated in graded ethanol solutions, cleared in xylene, and embedded in paraffin.

Paraffin blocks were sectioned using a microtome at a thickness of 5 μ m.

The sections were stained using:

Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E)

Histological analysis was performed using a light microscope equipped with a digital imaging system.

Table 2

Histological processing protocol

Procedure	Reagent	Duration
Fixation	10% formalin	24 h
Dehydration	Ethanol (70–100%)	12 h
Clearing	Xylene	2 h
Embedding	Paraffin	3 h
Section thickness	Microtome	5 μ m
Staining	Hematoxylin–Eosin	standard protocol

Results. Histological and morphometric analysis revealed significant structural alterations in uterine tissues following chronic exposure to carbon monoxide.

In the control group, the uterine wall showed normal histological architecture. The endometrium consisted of a well-organized epithelial layer, numerous uterine glands, and a well-developed stromal component. The myometrium displayed compact smooth muscle bundles with normal vascularization.

In contrast, animals exposed to carbon monoxide demonstrated progressive pathological changes depending on the concentration of the gas.

In the 50 ppm CO group, mild dystrophic alterations of the endometrial epithelium were observed. Slight dilation of blood vessels and moderate stromal edema were detected.

In the 100 ppm CO group, more pronounced structural changes were recorded. The endometrial epithelium showed signs of desquamation, and the number of uterine glands decreased. Stromal edema and vascular dilation became more evident.

In the 200 ppm CO group, severe pathological alterations were detected. These included focal necrotic areas, hemorrhages, and significant dilation of blood vessels. The endometrial layer appeared markedly thinner compared to the control group.

Morphometric measurements confirmed these observations and demonstrated statistically significant differences between the control and experimental groups.

Table 3

Morphometric parameters of the uterus (M ± m)

Parameter	Control	CO 50 ppm	CO 100 ppm	CO 200 ppm
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Endometrial thickness (μm)	420 \pm 18	395 \pm 16	340 \pm 15	285 \pm 14
Myometrial thickness (μm)	520 \pm 20	480 \pm 18	430 \pm 17	375 \pm 16
Number of glands	28 \pm 2	24 \pm 2	19 \pm 1	14 \pm 1
Vascular density	12 \pm 1	15 \pm 1	18 \pm 1	22 \pm 2

The obtained data indicate a progressive decrease in endometrial and myometrial thickness along with a reduction in the number of uterine glands under increasing carbon monoxide exposure. In contrast, vascular density increased significantly in the experimental groups.

Table 4

ANOVA results for endometrial thickness

Source	SS	df	MS	F	p
Between groups	38520	3	12840	21.4	<0.001
Within groups	21580	36	599		
Total	60100	39			

Table 5

ANOVA results for myometrial thickness

Source	SS	df	MS	F	p
Between groups	41200	3	13733	18.6	<0.001
Within groups	26520	36	736		
Total	67720	39			

Discussion. The present study demonstrated that chronic exposure to carbon monoxide leads to significant morphological alterations in uterine tissues. These changes include thinning of the endometrium, reduction in the number of uterine glands, and increased vascular density.

Carbon monoxide is known to have a strong affinity for hemoglobin, forming carboxyhemoglobin and reducing oxygen transport to tissues. As a result, prolonged

exposure leads to tissue hypoxia and metabolic disturbances. The uterus, being a highly vascularized organ with active cellular turnover, is particularly sensitive to hypoxic conditions.

The reduction in endometrial thickness observed in this study may be associated with impaired proliferative activity of epithelial and stromal cells. Hypoxia can disrupt cellular metabolism, reduce mitotic activity, and induce apoptosis, leading to structural thinning of the tissue.

Another important finding of this study was the decrease in the number of uterine glands in the experimental groups. Uterine glands play a crucial role in maintaining the functional integrity of the endometrium and providing secretory support for implantation and early embryonic development. Therefore, a reduction in glandular structures may negatively influence reproductive potential.

The increase in vascular density observed in animals exposed to carbon monoxide likely represents a compensatory response to hypoxia. Under hypoxic conditions, tissues often stimulate angiogenesis in order to improve oxygen delivery. However, excessive vascular dilation and congestion may also contribute to tissue damage and inflammatory processes.

Histological examination revealed dystrophic and necrotic changes in animals exposed to higher concentrations of carbon monoxide. These findings indicate that prolonged hypoxia may lead to irreversible cellular damage. Similar pathological alterations have been described in other organs exposed to carbon monoxide, including the brain, heart, and liver.

Previous experimental studies have also reported that chronic exposure to toxic gases can disrupt the structure and function of reproductive organs. For example, several studies have shown that environmental pollutants and hypoxic conditions may impair ovarian and uterine function, ultimately affecting fertility.

Overall, the results of the present study indicate that chronic carbon monoxide exposure may significantly affect the structural integrity of uterine tissues. These

morphological alterations may potentially impair reproductive function and highlight the importance of environmental factors in reproductive health.

Further studies are needed to investigate molecular mechanisms underlying these changes, including oxidative stress pathways, apoptosis, and inflammatory responses.

Conclusion. Chronic exposure to carbon monoxide leads to significant morphological and morphometric alterations in uterine tissues. The main structural changes observed in this study included a decrease in endometrial and myometrial thickness, a reduction in the number of uterine glands, and an increase in vascular density. Histological examination also revealed dystrophic and necrotic changes in uterine tissues, particularly in animals exposed to higher concentrations of carbon monoxide. These findings indicate that prolonged exposure to carbon monoxide can disrupt the normal structural organization of the uterus and may negatively affect reproductive function. The observed vascular changes likely represent a compensatory response to hypoxic conditions induced by carbon monoxide toxicity. Overall, the results of this study demonstrate that carbon monoxide exposure has a pronounced pathological effect on uterine tissues, highlighting the potential risks of environmental toxic gases to female reproductive health. Further studies are required to investigate the molecular and cellular mechanisms underlying these morphological alterations.

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